

Supplementary Information 3 – Trace element analyses

Concentrations of calcium (Ca), manganese (Mn), iron (Fe) and strontium (Sr) were measured on polished cross sections of the shells of *Campanile symbolicum* and *C. giganteum* using a Bruker M4 Tornado micro-X-Ray Fluorescence (μ XRF) scanner. The Bruker M4 is equipped with a 30 W Rh-anode X-ray tube that was operated at maximum energy settings (50 kV, 600 μ A). X-rays were focused on a round spot on the surface of the sample with a diameter of 25 μ m (Mo- $k\alpha$) using a polycapillary lens. Fluorescence X-rays emitted by the sample were detected by two silicon drift detectors in the Bruker M4 Tornado system. A high precision XYZ stage allowed non-destructive *in situ* analysis of sample composition with high spatial resolution. A vacuum chamber (20 mbar) reduced interference of air, improving signal-to-noise ratio on the low-energy end of the XRF spectrum (see de Winter and Claeys, 2017 for schematic setup).

Elemental abundances were mapped semi-quantitatively on complete surfaces of all shell cross sections by dragging the X-ray beam across the sample surface in two dimensions and recording spectra every 25 μ m (see de Winter and Claeys, 2016). The resulting dwell time on map pixels (1 ms) produces pixel spectra with signal-to-noise ratios insufficient for quantification, but X-ray peak integration of grouped spectra allowed relative changes in elemental concentrations to be visualized (**S4**). These maps allowed further assessment of shell preservation and guided sampling for stable isotope analysis.

Quantitative elemental concentration profiles were obtained through point-by-point line scanning on polished cross sections of the shells (see de Winter et al., 2017a). Scanning lines were positioned through the columella of the shells in growth direction, aided by the direction of growth in the shell determined in **S10** (see **Fig. S1**). For these profiles, a sampling density of 90 μ m and a dwell time of 60 s per point were chosen to compromise between measurement reproducibility and accuracy and spatial resolution (TSA and TSR; see discussion in de Winter et al., 2017b). μ XRF measurements were calibrated using a set of 7 matrix-matched carbonate standards: CCH-1 (Université de Liège, Belgium), COQ-1 (US Geological Survey, Denver, CO, USA), CRM393 (Bureau of Analyzed Samples Ltd, Middlesbrough, UK; BAS), CRM512 (BAS), CRM513 (BAS), ECRM782 (BAS) and SRM-1d (National Institute of Standards and

Technology, Gaithersburg, MD, USA). Reproducibility for all elements exceeded 5% relative to the mean (see **S3**).

Given the high detection limit of Mg in XRF measurements, quantitative abundances of this element were measured on powdered samples drilled from the outside of the shell of *C. symbolicum* and *C. giganteum* gastropods (see **Fig. S1** for sample locations). These are the same powdered samples as were used for stable isotope analyses. Samples of ~1 mg of powder were dissolved in 1 mL 14M subboiled distilled nitric acid (HNO₃, VWR, Leicestershire, UK) and digested overnight at 90°C until completely dissolved. The resulting solution was dried out on a hotplate and redissolved in 10 mL 1M HNO₃. Mg concentrations were determined using High-Resolution-Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (HR-ICP-MS, ELEMENT2, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., Waltham, MS, USA). Long term reproducibility of the count rate of the ICP-MS detector was assessed by spiking every sample with an in-house In solution (100 µg/L), and linearity within ICP-MS runs was corrected using this In data. Measurements of solution concentrations were calibrated using a double calibration method which involved an initial calibration using series of in-house standard solutions with concentrations ranging between 5 and 100 ppb (µg/L). These results were then recalibrated using a set of certified trace element reference materials (Bureau of Analyzed Samples CCB01, CRM513 and CRM782; National Institute of Standards and Technology SRM1486, SRM1400, SRM120c; US Geological Survey BEN and PMS; and in-house ENF and CBA; see de Winter et al., 2016), which were treated as samples throughout the sample preparation and measurement routine. Goodness of fit (R²) of the calibration curve for Mg was better than 0.999 for all measurement runs. Calibrated concentrations in solution were converted to concentrations of powdered samples using the dilution factor and by using Ca as internal standard (assuming a concentration of 38.5 wt%).

References

de Winter, N., Snoeck, C., & Claeys, P. (2016). Seasonal cyclicity in trace elements and stable isotopes of modern horse enamel. *PLoS ONE*, 11(11), 1. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0166678>

Fig. S1: Photos showing the position of XRF line scans as well as locations of external sampling for stable isotope analyses.